

**THE ROLE OF THE TEACHERS WITHIN A COMMUNICATIVE
LANGUAGE APPROACH**

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Annotation: *For a number of years, the communicative approach has been holding the leaders in the field of theory and methods of teaching foreign languages, which is why the communicative approach is so popular.*

Key words: *Communicative, communicative approach, methodology*

Over the last four decades, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) has been recognized as an ideal approach to help learners acquire a foreign language. This approach stemmed from the changes of the British language teaching tradition dating from the late 1960s. A lot of British linguistics contributed to the need for creating the Communicative Language Approach which seeks to make communicative competence, term which creates interdependence when talking about a communicative language approach, rather than grammatical structures, as central to teaching. Moreover, this approach mainly focuses on the development of communicative competence as its main objective through the foreign language as a means of communication in the class sessions.

In this sense, Canale and Swain explained the communicative competence based on four dimensions which assembled importance in the Communicative Language Teaching approach. These dimensions were defined as follows:

-Grammatical competence: It refers to the ability to make good use of grammar rules established in order to produce and understand a message.

-Sociolinguistic competence: It consists in the ability to use language in any social context.

-Discourse competence: it refers to the ability to connect a set of ideas correctly to understand, interpret and exchange message.

- strategic competence: it consists of being able to use abilities and communication strategies as a result of a lack of language (vocabulary, grammar complex, etc.)

The main goal to be achieved when using these skills is to be able to understand and being understood at the time.

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Having said that, it should be clear that communicative competence needs to be the core issue when it comes to teaching a language. That is, not only grammar should be considered when teaching a language, but it is also important to pay attention to the language used and their respective function.

Moreover, nowadays the CLT has become an important approach sufficiently recognized when teaching a language. This is because when referring to foreign language learners, they cannot really learn the target language well without paying close attention to this competence.

It is clear that the mission of educating our children any young learners falls directly on two essential pillars: family and school. Although in the field of the family the essential figure that will carry out the educational and social work are the parents; in the case of the school, the key subject of training is the teacher staff.

Nowadays the role of the teacher has changed from a transmitter of knowledge to a facilitator and a socializing agent who has an impact on the learning lives of children.

All this leads us to consider the utmost importance that have the role of teachers in a school setting, and the maximum responsibility to establish the principle relationships that occur in the student- teacher interactions in the classroom.

According to Prieto, at the time of undertaking the teaching practice, teachers should give themselves to this practice with the attitude of being an element of the class rather than the main one. The teacher should conceive of the teaching-learning process as community matter, in which all members of the group should participate. In this way, Prieto claims that: "communication between the students and the teacher will be enhanced, resulting in greater interaction and, certainly, a greater quality in the formative process of the group as a whole" [3; p:334]

We often fall into the error of thinking that anyone can teach a group of children, but all who dedicate to teaching know that is not quite like this. The education we must transmit to our children should not be only about a transfer of knowledge and content; it goes further. Prieto also states that all that surrounds the transmission of content must be accompanied by a training in revitalizing techniques, which can lead to a more direct and lasting communication, which at the time, allows the intercommunication between teacher and student and, therefore, create much more effective training.

Focusing on CLT, according Sauvignon, CLT theory is based on a proper educational environment, which requires an appropriate organization of several variables. To begin with, we need the experience and knowledge of teachers,

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students' needs as well as their attitudes are another variable to consider. In addition, we must not leave out the scene where the lessons are carried out, in this case, the classroom. In other words, a classroom, which promotes a communicative approach to language, is considered to be a social context where teachers and students are the key players, and the role they play is crucial for the performance of communicative teaching.

A class of CLT focuses mainly on creating an environment focused on the learner rather than an environment focused on the teacher. This fact requires that the role of teachers must be changed. Instead of being a class-dominator, as they were supposed to be in the past, they are shifted to become a class-supporter. Saying it in another way, Savignon also supports this idea of changes in roles, stating that:

"Autonomous learning influences teaching methodology and dramatically changes the roles of the language teacher and the language learner". To cope with these changes, future teachers have to be prepared both practically and academically. [4; p27].

In addition, other authors claimed that when it comes to carrying out a class of CLT, the role of teachers may vary accordingly. The flexibility of the teacher varies from manager, scheduler, driver, organizer, facilitator, etc. to support the learning of their students. In addition, to meet the need for language that learners have, it is necessary that the teacher implement tasks based on text, or other methods that require the teacher to play a role of adviser, analyst and process manager as well as in relation to this. Different roles are given to teachers in a communicative approach to language. Breen and Candlin summarize in their own words the role that have been already mentioned:

The teacher has two main roles: the first role is facilitates the communication process between all participants in the classroom, and between these participants and the various activities and texts. The second role is to act as an independent participant within the learning-teaching group. The latter role is closely related to the objectives of the first role and arises from it [1; p 99]

Applying CLT is also necessary that the teacher performs appropriate questions, encouraging the learners to answer actively and thus facilitating students' participation in classroom activities.

Having said that, we can conclude that the role teacher in a communicative approach to language is mainly based on three important factors. The teacher should be a facilitator, who classroom communication and establishes situations and contexts likely to promote communication. The teacher is also a co-communicator, participating in activities with their students. Finally, the teacher

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should be an advisor when presenting activities, answering questions from students and monitoring their performance.

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